

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF EDUCATION OF CHILDREN AS PERFECT HUMAN BEINGS

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Abstract. *In this article, the views and opinions of leading psychologists and pedagogues and Eastern thinkers on the combination of the influence of biological and external social environmental factors on the formation of a child as a perfect human being, the mental impact of the state of anomaly (regression) in the child's development, It is covered on the basis of research and several years of work experience.*

Keywords: *child's biological factors, social environment, child's anomaly (regress), historical thinking, education, child's psyche and its development, person, personality, individuality, formation of skills and competencies in the child.*

Looking at this issue as a psychological factor, the scientific views of leading practicing psychologists, who study the development of children's psyche, are noteworthy. Among others, S.L.Rubinstein, L.S.Vygotsky, Z.Freud, D.S.Hall, P.P.Blonsky, D.H.Jackson, F.Holsman, A.N.Leontev, A.R.Luria, E.Krechmer, J. Piaget, S.Scribner, K.Goldstein, G.S.Sullivan, Ya.Kazanin, H.Werner, B.Kaplan and many other psychologists have expressed valuable scientific and practical opinions and opinions on this problem. According to L.S.Vygotsky, one of the manifestations of psychological retardation of the child's development is the child's inability to master the concepts of words in relation to his age or the disproportion in his actions in relation to his age. The child cannot fully and qualitatively perform the task of managing his spiritual inner self, i.e. reflection in relation to the object of external influence. As a result, the child lags behind in development, and external and internal movement cannot provide the formation of mental characteristics, as a result, sharp imbalances in the child's actions compared to his peers begin to be felt. It can be seen that a child's personality develops not only under the influence of biological factors, but also under the influence of individual and social-psychological characteristics. It should be noted that there are theorists in the field of psychology who prioritize biological development over factors of psychological development. In particular, biogenetic theorists and Z.Freud and his students recognized that instincts controlling human activity are the main factor passed down from generation to generation - a trait, an innate product, a force that drives the initial unconscious needs and inclinations. In psychoanalysis, mental development means suppression of innate instincts by society and adaptation of the child to an environment that is opposite to the specific personality that was originally born. The relationship between the child and society is antagonistic. Society puts pressure on the child with the help of prohibitions and restrictions, as a result of which the child is formed as a person.

With this understanding of the relationship between heredity and environment, heredity became the leading factor, because it determined development, and the environment acted only as conditions for the implementation of hereditary fixed characteristics. Nevertheless, determining the role of each factor in mental development is one of the important problems.

S.Hall, strategic in studying the child, considered a comprehensive approach that allows the use of questionnaires to determine the problems of the child - in his understanding and from the point of view of adults.

Together with T.Simon, A.Binet developed the "metric scale of intellectual development". In addition to the idea that heredity plays a leading role in mental development, testology is based on the position that development occurs independently of learning and that learning follows and follows development.

An English geneticist Sh.Auerbach, believes that the level of mental development of a child, special abilities of a child, individual qualities of a child are innate, and these pre-existing factors determine the characteristics of the environment. Australian psychologist K.Bauler considered the genetic factor to be the leading factor not only in the mental development of a child, but also in the development of moral quality⁴, while the American psychologist and pedagogue D.Dewey said that "human nature cannot be changed, heredity determines human nature." supports the idea. The above-mentioned psychologists' and pedagogues' opinions about the child's personality and its formation are definitely a one-sided approach. , did not take into account factors such as education. In fact, in the field of psychology, there are concepts of man, person, and individuality, which harmonize with each other, but are qualitatively different from each other. If we look at man from a biological point of view, he belongs to the class of mammals, he is a biological creature, his ontogenetic development means that he walks upright, his hands are adapted to work, he has a highly developed brain, etc., and so on.

In terms of socialization, it is assumed that a person is armed with consciousness, through which he can perceive existence. As an individual, a person is an active conscious member of society, able to share his impressions with others based on certain standards based on his feelings and inclinations with the help of his speech, and influence others with his consciousness. 'tkaza is the possessor of consciousness.

Forming and educating young people's thinking on the basis of enlightenment is one of the most urgent tasks of today. "The youth of today's world is the largest generation in the history of mankind in terms of numbers, ... if we take into account the fact that they make up 2 billion people, the future of our planet, the well-being of our planet depends on how these young people mature into human beings". In this regard, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev proposed the development of a legal document on the development of multilateral international cooperation in social support of the young generation, protection of their rights and interests - the UN International Convention on the Rights of Youth. On September 20, 2017, he emphasized in his report at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly.

The individuality of a person is determined by the uniqueness of all people in the world, the uniqueness of each of them, their intellectual, emotional, volitional qualities. It can be seen from these that along with the innate vision, hearing, sensation, feeling, sensation and other features of human life, the influence of education and training on life conditions and activities is fundamental. It is filled with moral and normative qualities. In the words of the famous Russian psychologist S.L.Rubinstein, "... personality is a set of internal conditions that change the direction of external influences." Another problematic issue in the field of psychology, which has different views, is the question of which of the genetic, innate, acquired or social factors is the leader in the mental development of a person. For example, the anatomical-physiological features inherited by a child from their parents represent hands, feet, facial structure, etc. Psychologically, his adaptation to the environment, free movement, representation of things and events in his mind is considered a general process, and the extent to which it is performed differs in each person. Because when a person interacts with the outside world, the acquired or inherited anatomical anomaly (regression) (shortness of limbs, very low height, disproportion of body structure, etc.) affects the human psyche, has a negative impact on his place in society. Therefore, it cannot be denied that the external environment has an influence on the development of the child's psyche as a leading factor.

Leading psychologists L.S.Vygotsky, S.Rubinstein, A.Leontev, and others, while not denying the role of generational inheritance, recognized that the social environment is the leading factor in the formation of a child as a perfect person.

Psychologists V.N.Kolbonovsky, A.R.Luria and A.N.Mironov's researches show that³, even in twins from the same egg cell, in the same natural conditions, according to educational methods, combinatorial, that is, completely different results were obtained in certain types of creative activity. So, if we say that factors passed from generation to generation are the leading factors in the formation of a child as a perfect person, external factors are just a tool or social environment, and factors passed from parents through genes are not the main ones, we have made a mistake in both concepts. we will be If we can give the child proper education based on their equal and appropriate cooperation, then we will be able to shape the child into a perfect human being.

A number of social and biological factors such as properly organized education for the child, the character of the family and its members' interactions, the social groups with which the child communicates, the profession he chooses, the perfection of the child's internal mental capabilities. formation, self-awareness and attitude towards others, as well as its intellectual development. Many scholars of the East expressed their opinions on this. For example, Abu Nasr Farabi, in his work "The City of Virtuous People", made an excellent observation about man and his psyche, that the development of the human psyche is directly related to biological and environmental factors and is influenced by these factors. recognizes the formation.

Ibn Sina gave valuable information about the structure of the human body, its physiological processes and the mental factors that are directly connected with them, and their influence on the human body in his work "The Laws of Medicine".

The main issue in Yusuf Khos Hajib's work "Kutadgu Bilig" is the education of a perfect person, in Abdurrahman Jami's "Bahoristan", "Tuhfatul Ahror" and other works, the child is educated, enlightened, educational and professional. When thinking about teaching, Alisher Navoi in his works "Khazayinul-Maoni", "Mahbub-ul Qulub" and other works expressed excellent thoughts about a mature, perfect person, his morals and abilities. In addition, Babur, Furqat, Bedil, Farghani, Mashrab, Gulkhani, Nadira, Uvaisi, Muqimi, Zavqi, Avloni and many other thinkers, writers, poets and poetesses in their works also wrote about youth education, They paid special attention to character, issues of family life and interpersonal relations. So, scientifically based opinions and life experiences show that if a child does not come into the world from biologically healthy parents (if an anomaly (regression) is observed in the child), then it is spiritually It remains as a difficult problem to find a solution to form a balanced and perfect human being.

It is known that in our society, human health, physical fitness, and the possession of a culture of a healthy lifestyle are very important social values. Ensuring the health of the nation and preserving the gene pool of the nation can be solved in a sufficiently positive way only thanks to a healthy lifestyle. These are all social institutions of the society; family, educational institutions, neighborhood, and independent education, the issue of conveying the content and essence of a healthy lifestyle to the citizens of our society, raising young people to be alert, knowledgeable, well-rounded individuals.

Based on this, from the first years of independence, we began to create a healthy generation in our Republic. The issue of raising a "perfect generation" has risen to the level of state policy, and this issue has begun to be considered as a priority task.

However, despite the measures taken for the comprehensive development of young people in our country and the great attention paid to this field, among young people there are still vices such as smoking, addiction to alcohol, crime, showing immoral and inhuman behavior. In our

opinion, this is due to the insufficient formation of the psychology of a healthy lifestyle among young people and the general population, and especially in families.

One of the things being done in new Uzbekistan for the development of young people in all aspects is "Formation of a healthy lifestyle". we are used to imagining being free from bad habits. This term is explained primarily in relation to the activities of health workers. However, in the formation of a healthy way of life - body and mind, mind and perception are directly related to a person, so psychology, which is a science that studies the laws and secrets of the human psyche, is related to it. That's why there is a concept of healthy lifestyle psychology in the science of psychology, which looks at a healthy lifestyle first of all as a reflection of the human mind and thinking. Therefore, ensuring our health, which is as necessary for each of us as water and air, and getting used to a healthy lifestyle in order to achieve this, appears as a research subject not only of medical workers, but also of psychologists and the science of psychology.

In this sense, when psychology studies from the point of view of human behavior, behavior and various psychological states in the formation of a healthy lifestyle: basically, each of us has a seemingly mysterious psyche that makes us feel healthy, healthy and refreshed. what aspects are related to our actions, what possibilities are available in our hands to protect our wealth - our health by managing it, and the formation of the psychology of a healthy lifestyle allows each of us to manage our mental state, the changes taking place in our consciousness It is more and more boldly entering our life as a science and a useful practice that studies ways of keeping it moderate by progressing in time, adapting to changing conditions, prevention in this regard.

It is known from the sources that there are a number of social, economic, political, medical, physical, pedagogical, psychological and other factors for the formation of the psychology of a healthy lifestyle. In this article, we will discuss the psychological aspects of forming the psychology of a healthy lifestyle: human character; a person's attitude towards a healthy lifestyle; socio-psychological factors of healthy lifestyle formation; the role of individual-psychological characteristics of a person in the formation of the psychology of a healthy lifestyle; we want to reflect on the influence of the family environment in which a person grows up, that is, external social and psychological factors.

The factor of personal motivation plays a big role in the formation of a healthy lifestyle. And motivation, according to its content, means to move a person to perform a certain activity, to justify and understand its importance. In the issue of healthy lifestyle psychology, the motivational factor is focused on explaining to people why they should live in the environment of healthy lifestyle psychology, why they choose unhealthy lifestyle behavior.

In the Uzbek family, signs of multigenerational are clearly expressed. The adults of the family - grandfathers, grandmothers, close relatives, neighbors, and the neighborhood - directly participate in the formation of healthy ideas and knowledge in the child's mind. According to our age-old customs, grandparents, grandparents, neighbors and relatives have a stronger influence on the upbringing of our children than parents. They are the determinants of the spiritual environment in the family. This kind of education tradition is considered an important spiritual and pedagogical value left over from the past, and this kind of education style was formed in the life of our great ancestors and reached a certain level of system.

To sum up, psychologists have a great responsibility in carrying out the work that is being done for the development of young people in New Uzbekistan. We are used to imagine that "forming a healthy lifestyle" means first of all getting rid of harmful habits that cause the human body to become sick. Paying special attention to the factors that have a positive or negative effect on the development of children, in addition to the formation of a healthy lifestyle, imposes extremely responsible tasks on educators, teachers and parents. Among the conditions and factors

that they should pay attention to, we can show the following as examples: hereditary factors of the child passed from generation to generation, healthy or unhealthy environment in the family, organized for the child. hygienic or unhygienic environment, healthy and properly organized for the child or unhealthy educational environment inconsistent with the age of the child, environmental factors, technical and technological information attacks, etc. We can see that all factors play a role in the development of a child into a mature person in the future. In addition, genetics, i.e., their abilities, interests, and some character factors can be transferred from parents to the child in the future. After the birth of a child, it is necessary to take into account the role of healthy psychological environment created by parents, proper education, and the influence of the social environment on the child's formation. But another aspect is personal activism. If the child does not have personal activity, then the formation of the child as a mature person will be questioned. In addition, complex processes such as physical and psychological changes, physiological changes, and social adaptation occur that affect the child's psyche at each age in the formation of a child as a perfect human being. it would be expedient to pay attention to the proper development of the child in cooperation with neighborhood activists and owners of educational institutions.

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